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CHALLENGE THE SCHOLARS!

EDUCATIONAL ASSIGNMENT FOR UNDERGRADUATE DESIGN RESEARCH STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

The shift towards more conceptual and discursive design discipline requires changes on all the levels of design education including the first introductory modules. 'Challenge the Scholars' was a teaching experiment to introduce design literature and discuss its relevance in contemporary design practice with undergraduate design students. The driving motivation for the experiment was a need to find models to link theoretical studies and lessons on design thinking to a Bachelor of Arts program in design in a manner that would be motivating for students with practical and professional orientation. In the 'Challenge the Scholars' assignment the students interviewed design practitioners based on selected items of design literature and made the practitioners to respond on the scholars' interpretations based on their first-hand experience. The results of the experiment were promising: the students worked with high motivation and the results actually challenged the scholarly texts in interesting manners.

Keywords: Design education, design theory

INTRODUCTION

Academic design researchers, educators and consultants (e.g., Brown 2009, Burns et al 2006, Falin 2011, Krippendorff 2006, Thackara 2005, Valtonen 2007) agree on the scene of design changing towards essentially more immaterial, conceptual and discursive direction. Even though these ideas as such are nothing new (Simon 1969/1999), it seems that presently design is seen increasingly as an approach to identify, frame and solve wicked problems, to create new knowledge and facilitate social innovations. Consequently, the

aesthetics, material and product category based expertise as the foundation of design competence, while not perhaps becoming obsolete, is losing its ground as the only proper foundation of design competence. Thus, the turn towards conceptual, discursive and strategic design sets demands on design education and curriculum development many of which are still waiting for proper responses. The Bauhaus model of workshop-based education is hardly the only way to construct foundations for the emerging design expertise. However, it seems that the practical studio-based education has been the mainstream until recently especially in undergraduate design programs (Boucharenc 2006).

When design educators develop new curricula for more strategic and conceptual skill sets the attention is often focused on the postgraduate education. For instance, research driven design education and related PhD level programs as well as different types of cross-disciplinary programs are among the current solutions. For a reason not addressed here, the conceptual thinking and research competencies given during the first few years of design studies seem to be a blind spot (Keinonen & Koskinen 2007). The conceptual and discursive skills are not nourished, and according to the author's opinion an undergraduate design program with its utmost practical workshop approach factually makes the students to unlearn what they absorbed at high school about analytical thinking, working with literature and writing. The intention is not to suggest that reading and writing would be a shortcut to the contemporary design competence, but the author believes that ignorance on design thinking and design literature does not make facing the change any easier.

Consequently, the development of design research and design literature curricula for all the educational levels has become a challenge. The students need to get familiar with what has been written about design, its scope, practices, peculiarities, values, responsibilities and so on. However, the literature needs to be introduced so that the students' high motivation to learn will not be jeopardized with classics written before they - and their teachers - were born. Otherwise the danger is that the introduction to design literature works in contrary to the intentions and alienates students from research and theory driven approaches. Design students are the most eager to learn about the design practice and to get integrated in the professional design activities. The university is the route to design community but the interesting phenomena are typically seen to be outside of the academic environment. Thus, the literature should be connected to the contemporary practice to make it relevant at the moment and to ensure a motivating learning experience.

TEACHING EXPERIMENT

The author has recently, in fall 2010, explored with a student assignment that combined familiarizing with design research classics and contemporary discussions with the state-of-art design practice. 'Challenge the Scholars' was a short 2 ECTS assignment given to a group of 18 students most of whom were the first year undergraduate students of industrial design (ID) and some were majors in engineering and other subjects taking ID as a minor subject. The rationale of the assignment was to make the students to compare certain key aspects of design thinking in the mainstream design theory with the way contemporary design practitioners see the same issues appearing in their daily practice. The task provided the students an opportunity to meet design practitioners whose work they were interested in and means to discuss with them about design on a more meaningful level that would have been possible spontaneously.

The students, who worked in teams of two, were given a list of seminal publications in design, some widely read recent books and some locally written insights (Buchanan 2001, Cross 2006, Dreyfuss

1955/2003, Keinonen 2009, Kelley & Littman 2005, Lawson 2004, Loewy 1953/2003, Mutanen 2008, Papanek 1974/2006). The literatures covered topics such as the scope, values and approaches within design. The students' task was to study the material focusing on one text each and isolate a set of relevant topics to be addressed in a focus interview with a design practitioner. The students chose the texts they found the most interesting themselves based on the instructor's introductions. The students were also free to choose a practitioner whose opinions and views of design they were especially interested in. The selected practitioners included:

- three industrial designers,
- a glass designer,
- a team of packaging designers,
- a fashion designers and
- two furniture designers.

Based on the interview that lasted from 30 minutes to 1 hour, the students edited an essay about the practitioners' responses and gave a short presentation highlighting the main results.

For the educators wishing to replicate the process, the phases are specified in figure 1.

Figure 1. The phases of the student assignment.

RESULTS

The results of the interviews as such are obviously not the most important outcomes of the project. The sample was small and the students did not have previous experience with interviews. However, some results are presented here to demonstrate the way the assignment functioned. And the students indeed identified some interesting insights into the original sources and, thus, deserve to be mentioned also for that reason.

Perhaps the main lesson learned was the context sensitivity of many of the claims in design literature. Design scholars look at the design phenomena from certain angles, which have a profound impact on what they see. Much of the knowledge about designerly thinking, for instance, is based on architectural design practice. The importance of understanding the context and also positioning the authors is well known to academics, but not so clearly explicated in many of the texts about design practice. In the 'Challenge the Scholars' assignment several of the student teams chose 'wrong' types of interviewees, i.e. they asked practitioners to reflect on literature written from different angle or about different context than where the interviewees carry their practice. The classroom discussion about the reasons for the disagreements between the scholarly texts and practitioners' views turned out as good lessons to understand the versatility of the field of design.

For example, a fashion designer explicitly challenged Lawsons' (2004, 104) architectural design based ideas that the final design solution would gradually emerge during the design process and that the ending rule for design elaboration would be externally defined. On the contrary, the designer said that her sketches define the targets for the phase of work she understood as 'designing' so clearly that the end of the process is achieved at the exact moment when the form of the 3D model of a garment corresponds with the sketches. This leaves no ambiguity into the target setting and ending rule of design.

Another pair of students had interviewed an industrial design consultant specializing in tableware

and domestic interior products. For him the whole concept of explaining design as an interaction between a design agent and the object of design the way Cross (2006) and Buchanan (2001) do it is seriously limited and inadequate as it ignores the crucial part of the process - and the essential competence of a consultant - namely the dialogue between the designer and the client. For him the object of design was not a product or system but the client satisfaction.

A furniture designer was interviewed by a third team of students. The topics dealt with Buchanan's (2001) and Keinonen's (2009) ideas about the expanding scope of design. The furniture designer refused to see changes in the design industry that would not be anything but passing phenomena of superficial discourse. He anchored his design expertise, and did not hesitate to generalize, with permanently relevant product categories such as furniture. He did not claim the emerging practices not to exist, but categorized them as external to what he considered design practice.

A not so surprising result of the interviews was that many of the design classics were unknown to the design practitioners.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the 'Challenge the Scholars' assignment experiment turned out encouraging. The students had understood and identified essential claims in the literature and properly conducted the interviews. The practitioners did not just respond by agreeing on or rejecting the claims, but explained their insights and practices and linked their opinions with concrete design projects they had completed recently. Compared to the author's earlier experience with introducing design research literature to undergraduate students the 'Challenge the Scholar' assignment increased the students' motivation and quality of their work substantially. It made reading an integral part of something that the students were extremely eager to learn, namely the practitioners' up to date perception of the key aspects of design.

Design is becoming increasingly conceptual, immaterial and discursive. Educating future designers with advanced skills in design research and good knowledge in the design theory is thus necessary and it is not just a challenge of postgraduate education. Instead, means to integrate studies on design research and design literature into undergraduate curricula are needed too. Finding ways to do it in a manner that motivates practically oriented design students is not free of challenge. This paper reports a successful educational case 'Challenge the Scholar' introducing design literature and contemporary practice together for the first year bachelor students of Industrial design.

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